

Baltic MUPPETS

DELIVERABLE 1.6

REPORT ON THE LEGISLATION OF MUSSEL FARMING

Co-funded by
the European Union

Disclaimer: Baltic MUPPETS is co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Grant agreement number	101083785
Project title	Baltic MUPPETS Baltic Mussel Products for PET-foodS
Deliverable title	Report on The Legislation of Mussel Farming
Deliverable number	1.6
Deliverable version	1
Contractual date of delivery	31/01/2025
Actual date of delivery	31/01/2025
Document status	Final
Online access	To be published on Baltic MUPPETS website
Diffusion	Public
Nature of deliverable	RE- Document, Report
Work Package	1
Contributing partners	CRM
Author	Peter Krost, Susanne Woldmann (CRM)
Editor	Reviewed by Per Dolmer (BLR), Susanna Minnhagen (ECO), Tim Staufenberg (KMF), Maya Miltell (SUB)
Keywords	Mussel Aquaculture, Legislation, Baltic Sea

CONTENT

<i>Introduction</i>	5
<i>A practical guide for mussel farmers</i>	6
Sweden.....	6
Denmark.....	13
Germany.....	19
<i>Legal background</i>	28
EU legislation and policy	28
Maritime Spatial Planning	28
Natura 2000.....	28
Water Framework Directive (WFD).....	29
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD).....	29
EU Animal Health Law	30
Testing of mussels for human consumption.....	30
Mussels as animal feed.....	33
The Organic Production	34
National legislation	35
<i>Funding and support</i>	41
<i>Annex 1: Overview of Swedish procedure</i>	46
<i>Annex 2: Overview of Danish procedure</i>	47
<i>Annex 3: Overview of German procedure</i>	48

INTRODUCTION

Baltic MUPPETS is a three-year project supported by the Interregional Innovation Investment (I3) instrument. The project aims to create a new value chain for small Baltic Sea blue mussels by developing nutritious and high-quality pet food products. It focuses on investing in innovative techniques for underwater cultivation, harvesting and processing of the Baltic Sea's native blue mussel. This initiative is expected to support local economic development and increase quality employment opportunities. In addition, mussel farming is expected to provide several ecosystem services such as nutrient removal, water quality improvement and biodiversity enhancement. Baltic MUPPETS is a follow-up of the [BalticBlueGrowth \(BBG\) project](#), and support for farmers can also be found in the BBG reports.

This document is part of the project's Work Package 1: Prepare market and sustainable businesses for scale up. It describes the required documents and procedures to initiate, apply and get approval for the installation of mussel farms in the three Baltic Sea countries Germany, Sweden and Denmark. It also covers compliance to the regulations of the running operation, and the requirements for delivering mussel products into the market – as food, feed or for other purposes.

This document is intended to be a practical guide to assist potential farmers in orienting themselves in the complex field of legislation. While not emphasized in this document, potential farmers should be knowledgeable about the positive side effects of mussel farming for water quality and biodiversity, as this might help support applications and product marketing. The document is divided into three main chapters:

- The practical guide listing stepwise requirements,
- the regulatory background on the EU and national levels, and
- funding opportunities in the target areas.

The document reflects the legislative context set to the end of 2024. Several subjects are currently under revision, such as the necessity and potential limits regarding the analysis of neurotoxins in the EU. The structure of this document is such that it can be updated easily.

A PRACTICAL GUIDE FOR MUSSEL FARMERS

For any farm establishment, the prerequisite is that the basic business planning, such as technicalities, financing and market potential has been assessed for the specific site, and that there is a feasible case.

As local conditions influence the mussel growth and development, including factors such as salinity, available food particles, ice exposure, etc., it is important to establish the final use of the mussels at an early stage. This could be for human consumption, as animal feed, for “mussel seed” growing at another site or for other non-nutritive purposes.

The project BalticBlueGrowth developed many supportive documents for mussel farmers to plan site selection, harvesting and product development, such as [a factsheet with advice for mussel farmers](#), [good practices for mussel farming in the Baltic Sea](#), [environmental impacts](#) and [socioeconomic effects](#).

In the sections below the country specific procedure and requirements are described for the countries Sweden, Germany and Denmark.

Sweden

Marine spatial planning is an ongoing national mission in Sweden, implemented by the County Administrative Board (CAB) and the coastal municipalities. Planners at regional/local level have a lot of information at their disposal (i.e. maps, impact assessments, etc.), that is not publicly accessible. Finalizing the Swedish marine spatial plan will greatly simplify the understanding of what space is available for mussel farming.

For the west coast of (Skagerrak, Kattegat and Öresund) Sweden, the regulatory framework for mussel farmers is the same as applies to most of the EU. At the Swedish east coast, however, mussel harvest for human consumption is not allowed. This is due to a discussion among national regulators about how to design and implement a control program for this low-salinity area. The case described in this report concerns mussel farming on the Swedish east coast, where harvested mussels are processed into animal feed instead of food. Most guidelines are the same for all Swedish mussel farmers, but the parts that concern harvest and processing of feed follow a different regulation compared to food.

Site selection

As there is no public access to Swedish marine spatial planning it is required to find necessary information from other sources. The [public maps from Lantmäteriet](#) provide information about water ownership (private, municipality, state) and also about protected areas. The County Administrative Boards (CABs) provide [online GIS services](#) with various planning materials. [Swedish sea charts are available at Sjöfartsverket](#) (the Maritime Administration).

Figure 1. Example of a digital map in Lantmäteriet showing Natura 2000 areas.

Step 1

Identify available areas from published sources that are suitable for the purposes of the farmer. Exclude nature-protected areas, military areas, wind parks, waterways, fishery priority areas, etc.

Choose and prioritize the most suitable sites (optimally more than one), draw on a sea chart and sketch the planned facility as detailed as possible, including data on the type of farm (longline, SmartFarm, or other), required area, water depth at each site, mooring system, aspired annual production, etc.

Contact the authority County Administrative Board

Swedish coastal areas and thus mussel farm permits are administered by the respective County Administrative Board (CAB), which has to be contacted. At Gotland, the municipality has adopted their responsibilities.

In addition, the ownership of the water area and/or the adjacent land area has to be taken into account and a permit for use has to be given. In the case of state-owned water, an application for use of the water area has to be sent to the court Kammarkollegiet that handles the use of state-owned waters. Typically, waters that are close to shore are owned by the nearby landowner (including the municipality) and more exposed areas are owned by the state/government. In archipelagos, it is not uncommon that several landowners have shared authority of the water use, including fishing rights, in which case you have to get approval from their organisation. As the Swedish Coast Protection Law generally prohibits construction close to the shore, an exemption needs to be obtained by the local municipality.

Each county and region might have specific environmental and societal strategies and might impose different priorities. It is therefore advised to prepare for proposals of different water areas and contact the relevant CABs as well as local municipalities or rural developers respectively developers.

The contact with the CAB might be an iterative process, in the course of which the following detailed documents have to be provided:

- Proposal of the exact farm size, and type (longline, SmartFarm, bottom culture), including details like the number and size of substrates and other objects.
- Exact drawing of the position of the planned farm on a nautical chart including coordinates and dimensions.
- Planned harvest capacity per year.
- Technical description of the farming procedure according to requirements, which might include duration of use (all year, seasonal) and details of the potential input of materials into the sea (type and amount, such as lost materials, antifouling coatings etc.).
- Information about water exchange, water depth,
- Details of used vessel(s).
- Description and frequency of regular work, like maintenance, harvesting, controls, etc.

Also, check for industries, sewage outlets, etc., in the area. The local municipality can give you a map that shows where they are and inform you about toxic sediments (or where to find this information). In the water planning tool [VISS](#) you can find information

about pollution sources, polluted areas, environmental data, measures taken and planned, etc. An easier version of the map of potentially polluted areas and sources is the [EBH-map](#).

The CABs oversee and implement the rules regarding environmental safety. In all cases, the farm must comply with the EU regulations and directives on habitats, species protection and water quality (see **EU legislation and policy**).

In some cases, the planned area collides with areas of military interest, which are not always marked on maps. In those cases, the water owners will decline the application without further explanation.

Action	Contact
Apply for a permit to deploy the mussel farm.	The relevant CAB.
Contact the relevant water owner to apply for permit of water use.	For state-owned water: Kammarkollegiet . For other waters the respective owner needs to be contacted, e. g. municipalities, organizations or private people.

Permit to deploy navigation aids and shipping rules

The permit is issued by the Swedish Transport Agency (Traffikverket), which also is in charge of control. The permit is required for appropriate marking of the farm site at sea and in the sea charts.

Work vessels used to manage the mussel farm must also be registered at the Swedish Transport Agency. Boats need to be equipped according to the safety requirements valid for the operational area (See **Shipping rules**).

There are various requirements for operating a boat, as well as the respective qualifications for the nautical staff, depending on the size of the vessel, the number of people on the boat and the operational area. Information can be obtained at the Swedish Transport Agency.

Action	Contact
Apply for a permit to deploy navigation aids.	Swedish Transport Agency, Transport Styrelsen, Tillstånd för sjösäkerhetsanordningar (SSA) - Transportstyrelsen
Register vehicles	

Mussel farming needs to comply with requirements according to the EU Animal Health Law. To get your aquaculture business approved by these requirements, it is required to register at the Swedish national database for aquaculture. You will then be assigned a contact person and asked to make a bio-safety plan (your contact will guide you through this process).

Action	Contact
Register the farm in the database " Sök vattenbruk ".	The Swedish Board of Agriculture, Jordbruksverket.

Depending on the judgement of the Swedish Institute for Veterinary Medicine, a control visit by a veterinarian at the farm might be required.

Public perception

Public perception is a very important, however often overlooked aspect. Particularly in near-shore environments where farms are visible from shore, or in areas of high recreational use, mussel farms might be considered physically or aesthetically disturbing and provoke opposition. It is advised to inform and include the relevant (local) stakeholders before installation and inform them about the benefits of mussel farming and discuss ideas for mutual peaceful coexistence. It might be useful to organize public events to inform relevant groups of people. Guidance and examples are given in the BBG factsheet "[Advice for the future Baltic mussel farmer](#)" and [final report](#).

Action	Examples of important stakeholders
It is advised to take the issue of public perception into account in advance and contact important stakeholders.	Tourist agencies, yacht or boat harbours, communal administrations, etc.

Processing of mussels for human consumption

As the establishment of mussel processing facility plants needs to be officially permitted, it is mandatory to contact the regional authority / municipality of the locality in which it is to be established. The permits encompass an environmental as well as a building permit, both issued by the respective municipality. The environmental permit regards waste and sewage, and the building permit certifies that the facility is in accordance with the local building requirements.

Harvest of mussels for human consumption is **currently not allowed** for the Baltic proper!

Livsmedelsverket, the National Swedish Food Agency, defines the requirements and authorize the sale of foodstuff. In the case of mussels, the main and most crucial points are toxins and potentially harmful microbes that need to be tested according to a scheme to be developed in cooperation with the National Swedish Food Agency.

Action	Contact
Request building permit for processing facility.	Respective municipality.
Request environmental permit for waste and sewage from processing facility.	Respective municipality.
Get food sale authorization from Livsmedelsverket.	Livsmedelverket, The National Swedish Food Agency

Mussels as animal feed

For the transport of feed mussels, the Swedish Agricultural Board has agreed that as long as the mussels are alive, they are by definition not animal by-products. So, during harvest and transport to the factory, feed and food mussels do not need to be kept apart.

The transporter should be a registered feed transporter and if dead mussels are transported, the transport must also be approved for transport of animal by-products.

Mussel feed producers must inform national authorities of the products and premises they use during the manufacturing chain. The manufacturing chain must meet hygiene standards and requires formal approval. The relevant authority is the Swedish Board of Agriculture which must be contacted as early as possible. Registration at the Swedish Board of agriculture is mandatory for any feed production facility within Sweden.

Action	Contact
Register a feed production facility at the Swedish Board of Agriculture.	Jordbruksverket, the Swedish Board of Agriculture
Register transporter for feed or animal by products	

Certification

KRAV is a Swedish label for organic food, feed and aquaculture. The KRAV Standards comply with the EU regulation for organic production, see **The Organic Production Regulation**.

Label	Certifier
Follow the KRAV procedure for certification.	KRAV-certification bodies

Denmark

Planning for your mussel farm in Denmark is simplified compared to Sweden as the Danish territorial waters are categorized in different zones for various uses and activities. Some areas are particularly designated for mussel production.

Site selection

Denmark has established a marine spatial plan, the [Havplan](#), where the marine area is separated into different zones, including a zone for mussel farming (marked as Ao). Since allowed areas are already defined, no further spatial planning is required and potential conflicts with other users (nature-protected areas, military areas, wind parks, waterways, fishery priority areas, etc.) are avoided.

Step 1
<p>Identify available areas from published sources that are suitable for the purposes of the farmer. Exclude nature-protected areas, military areas, wind parks, waterways, fishery priority areas, etc.</p> <p>Choose and prioritize the most suitable sites (optimally more than one), draw on a sea chart and sketch the planned facility as detailed as possible, including data on the type of farm (longline, SmartFarm or other), required area, water depth at each site, mooring system, aspired annual production, etc.</p>

Step 2	Contact
<p>Apply for permission for mussel farming at the Danish Fisheries Agency, an authority under the Ministry of Food, Agriculture, and Fisheries.</p>	<p>Danish Fisheries Agency mail@fiskeristyrelsen.dk</p>

Detailed planning

In many cases and due to various constraints, the areal extent of single mussel farms is limited. Therefore, in order to run a profitable mussel farming business, it is beneficial to have production across multiple farms. To improve the efficiency of the human capital, as well as investments in vessels and other equipment, it is important to maximize the number of days which allow for working at sea. Multiple mussel farms oriented differently in relation to wind exposure can enable more continuous work without interruptions due to weather conditions.

Production in multiple areas also offers the advantage of greater supply security for the established market. Geographically dispersed farms provide additional benefits in cases of toxic algae or microbiological issues, as the spread ensures a higher likelihood of being able to supply mussels to the market despite localized problems.

Step 3

For planning at a farm, the following details should be documented as part of the application process (marked with *), and some are for optimizing the production (marked with □):

- Proposal of the exact farm size, type (longline, smart-farm, bottom culture), number and size of substrates and other objects (*)
- Exact drawing of the position of the planned farm on a nautical chart including coordinates and dimensions (*)
- Envisaged production volume per year (□)
- Detailed technical description of the farming procedure (□)
- Maximum stocking (weight) at harvest time (*)
- Duration of use (all year, seasonal) (□)
- Details of the potential input of materials into the sea (type, amount) (*)
- Estimates of emission of faeces and proposed measures to minimize these emissions (□)
- Details of the used vessel(s) (□)
- Description and frequency of regular work, like maintenance, socking, harvesting, controls, etc. (□)

The municipality resp. administration unit to which the area belongs is responsible for each sea area, and this is the point of contact for further planning and permissions.

Environmental permit

Establishment of mussel farms requires environmental permission. Responsible for the environmental permit is the Danish Fisheries Agency (DFA). The DFA is in charge of evaluating the potential environmental impacts of the planned operation, based on the information provided in step 3. Overarching guidelines for an evaluation by the DFA is the compliance with the EU environmental legislation (WFD, MSFD, FFH) which requires GES in all surficial waters within the EU.

Fisheries permit

In Denmark, mussels fall under the same category as fish in the regulatory documents, and thus, the establishment of a mussel farm requires a fisheries permit by the Fishing Agency. The permit can be obtained by the Danish Agricultural Agency in the Ministry

for Food, Agriculture and Fisheries. A similar permit is also needed in the case of dredging of bottom cultivated or wild mussels.

Step 4	Contact
Present planning and ask for a permit.	Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri: Holbergsgade 6, 1057 København K fvm@fvm.dk Phone: +38 10 60 00

Aquatic Animal Disease

Mussel farming needs to comply with requirements according to the EU Animal Health Law. Depending on the judgement of the environmental authority, a qualified opinion of the respective veterinarian might be required. As veterinaries are subject to rural districts resp. municipalities, relevant contacts can be issued by the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA).

Step 5	Contact
Contact DVFA and ask how to proceed.	Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA): Stationsparken 31-33, DK-2600 Glostrup Phone: +45 72 27 69 00

Military and Navigation

Sea charts show the location of restricted areas for military purposes. However, there are additional areas that are being used for training and non-disclosed purposes which are not shown in sea charts. Furthermore, a number of coastal areas have been designated as places of refuge for ships in need of emergency shelter, where there is only a very limited risk of pollution.

Step 6	Contact
Check the farm placement with the provided addresses, to avoid collision with military interests or refuge areas for ships in need	Danish Maritime Authority: Caspar Brands Plads 9, 4220 Korsør Mail: sfs@dma.dk

Public perception

Public perception is a very important, however often overlooked aspect. Particularly in near-shore environments where farms are visible from shore, or in areas of high recreational use, mussel farms might be considered physically or aesthetically disturbing and provoke opposition. It is advised to inform and include the relevant (local) stakeholders before installation and inform them about the benefits of mussel farming and discuss ideas for mutual peaceful coexistence. It might be useful to organize public events to inform relevant groups of people.

In Denmark, negative perceptions and opposition against mussel farms have turned into a major obstacle to the installation of new mussel farms. As the respective municipalities are the permitting authorities, regional and local opposition has led to the rejection of permits in the past years.

Step 7	Example of important stakeholders
It is advised to take the issue of public perception into account in advance and contact important stakeholders.	Tourist agencies, yacht or boat harbours, communal administrations, etc.

Vessels

The Maritime Shipping law controls the use of ships on national and international waterways on the basis of the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea. Most likely, the mussel farm operation will need a suitable vessel. Boats need to be equipped according to the safety requirements valid for the operational area.

There are various requirements for operating a boat, again depending on the size of the vessel, the number of people on the boat and the operational area, as well as the respective qualifications for the personnel. Specific information can be obtained from the Danish Maritime Authority.

Step 8	Contact
Obtain vessel and operational permits.	Danish Maritime Authority: Caspar Brands Plads 9, 4220 Korsør sfs@dma.dk

Mussels for human consumption

An area for the production of mussels for human consumption can only be designated as such, if samples show no signs of toxic algae, algal toxins, or microbiological contamination (see **Testing of mussels for human consumption**).

In practice, fishermen or farmers collect water and mussel samples during the week before the beginning of the harvest and on the first day of harvesting. The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA) within the Danish Ministry for food, agriculture and fisheries is the point of contact for questions regarding sanitary aspects of the production facility. DVFA determines the frequency and type of sampling, means of sample transport and analysis, and assesses these samples to determine which production areas can be opened and classified for fishing and harvesting mussels, among other activities.

Mandatory analyses of mussel meat are:

- Environmental toxins (heavy metals, organic toxins): twice a year.
- Microbiology and algae toxins: For each harvest batch.

In the case of frequent harvesting and constant low concentrations of toxins, the sampling frequency can be reduced in consultation with the veterinary office.

	Contact
Contact the DVFA via phone or email. They will lead you through the process	The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA) : <i>Stationsparken 31-33, DK-2600 Glostrup</i> <u>Phone</u> : +45 72 27 69 00
Contact the Danish Ministry for food, agriculture and fisheries via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri: <i>Holbergsgade 6, 1057 København K</i> <u>Phone</u> : +45 38 10 60 00 <u>Mail</u> : fvm@fvm.dk

Mussels as animal feed

Mussel and mussel meal producers must keep a record of the products and transport (see **Mussels as animal feed**). They must inform national authorities of the products and premises they use during the manufacturing chain. The manufacturing chain must meet hygiene standards and requires formal approval.

Action	Contact
Contact the DVEA via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA): <i>Stationsparken 31-33, DK-2600 Glostrup</i> Phone: +45 72 27 69 00
Contact the FVM via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri (FVM): <i>Holbergsgade 6, 1057 København K</i> Phone: +45 38 10 60 00 fvm@fvm.dk

Certification

Product value can be increased by producing according to the standards of organic production or other sustainability certification schemes (see **The Organic Production Regulation and Certification**).

Labels	Certifier
EU Organic , ASC and MSC	Bureau Veritas

Germany

Germany follows EU legislation and differences to other countries are mainly regarding the classification of production areas according to microbiology, which needs to be determined before any commercial farming activity. Most of the points of contact are centralised in the state ministries or subordinated agencies.

Site selection

Finding a suitable place for a mussel culture without conflicts with other users and uses is one of the main challenges in the crowded and intensely used German territorial waters of the Baltic Sea.

For an overview of the existing use of the EEZ, you find interactive sea charts on the websites of Bundesanstalt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie ([BSH](#)).

Ostsee: Nutzungen und Schutzgebiete

Figure 2. Uses of German Baltic Sea waters. Source: BSH.

Step 1	
<p>Identify available areas from published sources that are suitable for the purposes of the farmer. Exclude nature-protected areas, military areas, wind parks, waterways, fishery priority areas, etc.</p> <p>Choose and prioritize the most suitable sites (optimally more than one), draw on a sea chart and sketch the planned facility as detailed as possible, including data on type of farm (longline, SmartFarm or other), required area, water depth at each site, mooring system, aspired annual production, etc.</p>	
Step 2	Contacts
<p>Contact the Maritime Spatial Authority (WSA for territorial waters, BSH for the EEZ) and present the preliminary planning. The authority will reject or approve the suggested sites. The WSA is also helpful in finding alternative sites.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In case of rejection: Look for other potential sites and go back to the WSA/BSH. • In case of preliminary approval: incorporate the advice from WSA/BSH into the plan(s) and proceed. 	<p>Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsamt Ostsee (WSA): Moltkeplatz 17, 23566 Lübeck</p> <p>Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie (BSH): Bernhard-Nocht-Straße 78, 20359 Hamburg</p> <p>posteingang@bsh.de</p>
Step 3	
<p>After a preliminary positive response from WSA or BSH, create a detailed outline, which has to include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proposal of the exact farm size, type (longline, smart-farm, bottom culture), number and size of substrates and other objects, • exact drawing of the position of the planned farm on a nautical chart including coordinates and dimensions, • envisaged production volume per year, • detailed technical description of the farming procedure, • maximum stocking (number, weight) at harvest time, duration of use (all year, seasonal), • details of the potential input of materials into the sea (type, amount), • estimates of emission of faeces and proposed measures to minimize these emissions, • details of the used vessel(s), • description and frequency of regular work, like maintenance, socking, harvesting, controls, etc. and send detailed plan to the WSA/BSH for approval. 	

River and shipping police permit

Once the detailed plan is approved, a river- and shipping police permit is issued. This process can be iterative if further information is asked for. The permit granted is temporary; a maximum duration of 25 years is possible but up to negotiation with the authority.

There is no private ownership of the water area; in case of overarching societal interests, the permit can be withdrawn. It is therefore recommended to discuss the modalities of such cases, and the responsible authority should be helpful in finding new suitable areas, covering potential costs for moving, environmental assessments and loss of harvest. However, this should be discussed and agreed upon early.

In recent years, ammunition from past wars has moved into the focus. If a survey for ammunition is required, also discuss the allocation of the costs with the authorities, as these can be significant.

Step 4	Contact
For the Exclusive Economic Zone, EEZ. contact the BSH via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie (BSH): Bernhard-Nocht-Straße 78, 20359 Hamburg posteingang@bsh.de
For Schleswig-Holstein and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern , contact the WSA via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsamt Ostsee (WSA): Moltkeplatz 17, 23566 Lübeck

Environmental permit

With the river- and shipping police permit and the detailed plan in hand, contact the Environmental Agency. The state ministries Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Ländliche Räume, Europa und Verbraucherschutz (MLLV) in Schleswig-Holstein and Ministerium für Klimaschutz, Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume und Umwelt (MKLLU) in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern (in cooperation with the subordinated agencies LFU – Landesamt für Umwelt and LUNG – Landesamt für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Geologie) will check and permit according to the laws of nature protection (Naturschutzrecht).

This is a more complicated step, and in most cases – according to the judgement of the authority - will require an environmental impact assessment (EIA). Depending on the size and location of the planned facility, an EIA can be costly and time-consuming.

For the environmental approval it is of great interest that the intended operation is not in conflict with the EU law regarding the environment, particularly the EU directives **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**, **Water Framework Directive (WFD)** and the **EU Natura 2000** network.

Step 5	Contact
<p>For the Exclusive Economic Zone, EEZ, contact the BMUV via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.</p>	<p>Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit und Verbraucherschutz (BMUV): <i>Stresemannstraße 128-130, 10117 Berlin</i> Phone: +49 228 993 050</p>
<p>For Schleswig-Holstein, contact the MLLV via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.</p>	<p>Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume, Europa und Verbraucherschutz (MLLV): <i>Fleethörn 29-31, 24103 Kiel</i> Mail: poststelle@mllv.landsh.de Phone: +49 431 988 0</p>
<p>For Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, contact the MKLLU via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.</p>	<p>Ministerium für Klimaschutz, Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume und Umwelt (MKLLU): <i>Paulshöher Weg 1, 19061 Schwerin</i> Mail: poststelle@lm.mv-regierung.de Phone: +49 385 588 0</p>

Fisheries permit

As mussels are considered to be “fish” in the policy context, and a fisheries permit is also needed for harvest. The MLLV in Schleswig-Holstein resp. MKLLU in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern will usually confirm that the planned project is in accordance with the fisheries laws, or ask for additional information. The permit will be issued by the responsible fishery department.

Step 6	Contact
<p>For the Exclusive Economic Zone, EEZ, contact the BLE via phone or email. They will lead you through the process..</p>	<p>Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung (BLE): Phone: +49 (0)228 6845-0 info@ble.de</p>

<p>For Schleswig-Holstein, contact the MLLV and LFU via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.</p>	<p>Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume, Europa und Verbraucherschutz (MLLV): <i>Fleethörn 29-31, 24103 Kiel</i> poststelle@mllev.landsh.de Phone: +49 431 988 0</p> <p>Landesamt für Umwelt (LFU): <i>Hamburger Chaussee 25, 24220 Flintbek</i> poststelle.flintbek@lfu.landsh.de Phone: +49 4347 704-0</p>
<p>For Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, contact the MKLLU and LALLF via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.</p>	<p>Ministerium für Klimaschutz, Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume und Umwelt (MKLLU): <i>Paulshöher Weg 1, 19061 Schwerin</i> poststelle@lm.mv-regierung.de Phone: +49 385 588 0</p> <p>Landesamt für Landwirtschaft, Lebensmittelsicherheit und Fischerei MV (LALLF): <i>Thierfelderstraße 18, 18059 Rostock</i> poststelle@lalf.mvnet.de Phone: 0385-588-61000</p>

Classification as a mussel production area

This point is relevant to whether harvested mussels are intended to be sold as human food or for other applications. Mussels that are produced for the purpose of human consumption may only be harvested from designated production areas that are monitored under food law. The production areas are classified into one of the three possible classes A, B or C. Based on microbiological criteria (*E. coli* content), the classification can change after each sampling.

Live bivalve molluscs harvested in class A production areas can be marketed for direct human consumption. Mussels from class B and C areas can only be sold for human consumption after they have been relayed or processed in a purification center.

The procedure to have an unclassified site classified is lengthy (6 months to 1 year) and very costly. It is therefore advisable to find a site with classification A from the start.

If there is no chance to find a suitable already classified area, **the responsible authority should be contacted at a very early stage**. This is followed by an examination of all existing documents. Together with the authority, the requirements including sampling and analysis scheme will be developed. A sampling period of a minimum of 6 months needs to be done before a first harvest permit is given.

The following steps need to be passed:

1. List of potential (or actual) sources of pollution, including a description of the main current directions.
2. Analysis of mussels within the projected area during one year, including microbiology (*E. coli*), algae toxins (ASP, DSP, PSP) and environmental toxins (see **Testing of mussels for human consumption**).
3. Also during one year, monthly samples of phytoplankton, with an emphasis on species that can be potentially harmful (*Alexandrium*, *Anabaena*, *Lyngby*, *Oscillatoria*, *Gymnodinium*, *Prorocentrum*, *Pseudo-Nitzschia*).

Step 7	Contact
For the Exclusive Economic Zone, EEZ., contact the BLE via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung (BLE): Phone: +49 (0)228 6845-0 info@ble.de
For Schleswig-Holstein, contact the MLLV and LFU via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume, Europa und Verbraucherschutz (MLLV): Fleethörn 29-31, 24103 Kiel poststelle@mlev.landsh.de Phone: +49 431 988 0 Landesamt für Umwelt (LFU): Hamburger Chaussee 25, 24220 Flintbek poststelle.flintbek@lfu.landsh.de Phone: +49 4347 704-0
For Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, contact the MKLLU and the LALLF via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Ministerium für Klimaschutz, Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume und Umwelt (MKLLU): Paulshöher Weg 1, 19061 Schwerin poststelle@lm.mv-regierung.de Phone: +49 385 588 0 Landesamt für Landwirtschaft,

	Lebensmittelsicherheit und Fischerei MV (LALLF): <i>Thierfelderstraße 18, 18059 Rostock</i> poststelle@lallf.mvnet.de Phone: 0385-588-61000
--	---

Aquatic Animal Disease

Mussel farming needs to comply with requirements according to the EU Animal Health Law (see **EU Animal Health Law**). Depending on the judgement of the environmental authority, a qualified opinion of the respective veterinarian might be required.

Step 8	Contact
Contact the veterinary which is responsible for your area via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Veterinary contacts in Schleswig-Holstein and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern

Military and Navigation

Sea charts show the location of restricted areas for military purposes. However, there are additional areas that are being used for training and non-disclosed purposes which are not shown in sea charts.

Normally, the WSA or the BSH will inform the applicant of possible military activities in the selected area.

Step 9	Contact
Check the farm placement with the addresses provided., to avoid collision with military interests.	BSH, Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie: <i>Bernhard-Nocht-Str. 78, 20359 Hamburg</i> Marinestützpunkt Kiel-Wik: <i>Schweriner Straße 17a 24106 Kiel;</i> Phone: +49 431 71745-1410 or +49 151 1462 604

Public perception

Public perception is a very important, however often overlooked aspect. Particularly in near-shore environments where farms are visible from shore, or in areas of high

recreational use, mussel farms might be considered physically or aesthetically disturbing and provoke opposition. It is advised to inform and include the relevant (local) stakeholders before installation and inform them about the benefits of mussel farming and discuss ideas for mutual peaceful coexistence. It might be useful to organize public events to inform relevant groups of people.

Step 10	Example of important stakeholders
It is advised to take the issue of public perception into account in advance and contact important stakeholders.	Tourist agencies, yacht or boat harbours, communal administrations, etc.

Vessels

Most likely, the mussel farm operation will need a suitable vessel. Boats need to be equipped according to the safety requirements valid for the operational area.

There are various requirements for operating a boat, again depending on the size of the vessel, the number of people on the boat and the operational area (see **Vessels**).

Step 11	Contact
Obtain vessel and operational permits. Contact and inform yourself at the provided addresses. They will guide you through the process.	BG-Verkehr, Berufsgenossenschaft Verkehr. BMDV, Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verkehr - Deutsche Flagge.

Mussels for human consumption

The relevant veterinary office is responsible for monitoring mussel processing on land, which is also the first point of contact for questions regarding sanitary aspects of the production facility. The veterinary office determines the frequency and type of sampling, means of sample transport and analysis. Mandatory analyses of mussel meat are:

- Environmental toxins (heavy metals, organic toxins): twice a year.
- Microbiology and algae toxins: For each harvest batch.

In the case of frequent harvesting and constant low concentrations of toxins the sampling frequency can be reduced in consultation with the veterinary office.

Action	Contact

Contact the Veterinary responsible for your area via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Schleswig-Holstein Mecklenburg-Vorpommern
--	--

Mussels as animal feed

Mussel and mussel meal producers must keep a record of the products and transport (see **Mussels as animal feed**). They must inform national authorities of the products and premises they use during the manufacturing chain. The manufacturing chain must meet hygiene standards and requires formal approval.

Action	Contact
Contact the veterinary responsible for your area via phone or email. They will lead you through the process.	Schleswig-Holstein Mecklenburg-Vorpommern

Certification

Labels such as Naturland and ASC encompass the EU standard, adding particular and specific values such as animal welfare or social standards (see **The Organic Production Regulation**).

Label	Certifiers
Naturland , Bioland , EU Organic	E.g. ÖkoP , ABCert , TÜV Nord , Gruenstempel , GfRS and EcoCert .
ASC and MSC	

LEGAL BACKGROUND

In this section, we present the relevant legislation and directives of EU and national level relevant and in force at the time of the preparation of this report (end of 2024). Due to ongoing political and environmental development, there might be changes in future, which cannot be covered here. In addition, local regulations might be in force which are also not covered here. In the latter case, it is advised to refer to the local administration to seek information.

EU legislation and policy

Maritime Spatial Planning

To ensure sustainable use of the sea, the Directive 2014/89/EU was adopted to implement maritime spatial planning into national policy. According to this Directive, Member States are obliged to develop national maritime spatial plans. Thereby, “Member States shall consider economic, social and environmental aspects to support sustainable development and growth in the maritime sector, applying an ecosystem-based approach, and to promote the coexistence of relevant activities and uses” (Art. 5, 2014/89/EU).

Natura 2000

Natura 2000 is an EU-wide network of protected areas for the protection of endangered or typical habitats and species. The Natura 2000 network consists of the bird directive (directive 2009/147/EG) and the protected areas according to the Habitats Directive (directive 92/43/ EWG).

Important rules for protection are the ban of deterioration, and the need for FFH-impact assessment. Any projects (constructions, use) must be evaluated with respect to the potential of the protected area. Whereas a sustainable use of these areas is not necessarily entirely ruled out, severe damages – particularly irreversible changes - are forbidden. In or near Natura2000 areas, permission for mussel fishing on both longlines, SmartFarm systems and from wild populations may be restricted, if fishing takes place where significant, negative effects on certain species or habitats are unavoidable. The permit licences are dependent on the conservation of eelgrass and reefs, and thus, mussel fishing is distributed along specific depth zones, with the aim of having little to no impact on existing eelgrass populations.

Water Framework Directive (WFD)

The EU inland and coastal water policy is regulated by the WFD (Directive 2000/60/EC). The most important aims of the WFD (Art. 4a) are the prevention of further deterioration of the status of all bodies of surface water and achieving good surface water status. The WFD aims at European lakes, rivers, transitional (estuaries and lagoons) and coastal waters to a distance of 1 nautical mile (nm) for the ecological status resp. 1 nm for the chemical status from the baseline. The chemical status classification is determined by a body of surface water in which concentrations of pollutants do not exceed the environmental quality standards established in Annex IX and X, and according to the Environmental Quality Standard (EQN) Directives from 2013 article 4 (and Annex V point 1.4.3.). The ecological status classification is

determined for each water body by applying a range of biological quality elements, supported by hydromorphological and physicochemical quality elements (Annex V).

Aquaculture affects and interacts with water, at the same time requiring high-quality water to guarantee the health of farmed animals, and safe and high-quality products. Expected major impacts through mussel farming are;

- mooring,
- shading,
- accumulation of organic material (faeces /pseudofaeces),
- change of currents,
- introduction of chemicals (fuel and lubricants) and lost equipment (floats, ropes),
- disturbance of marine fauna (injury, noise), and
- disturbance of landscape scenery.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)

The MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC) applies to marine waters, beyond coastal waters covered by the WFD (> 1 nm from baseline and including the EEZ) and aims to achieve GES of EU marine waters by 2020.

So far, few mussel farms are in areas relevant to the MSFD, but future development including the co-use of wind parks will probably change that. Probable and major impacts through mussel farming are similar as in the case of WFD (**see Water Framework Directive (WFD)**).

EU Animal Health Law

The EU Animal Health Law (Regulation (EU) 2016/429 on transmissible animal diseases) aims to prevent and control animal diseases that can be transmitted to other animals or humans and to strengthen the enforcement of health and safety standards for the entire agri-food chain. It includes the prevention and control of certain diseases in aquatic animals and specifies animal health requirements for the sale, import or transit of aquaculture animals (farmed fish and shellfish at all their life stages), minimum measures to increase general awareness and prevent disease and to minimise measures in the event of a suspected, or established, outbreak of disease. It encompasses requirements regarding traceability (Art. 8), implementation of good hygiene practices (Art. 9) and risk-based health surveillance (Art. 10).

Farmed shellfish must be healthy. The EU may decide to inspect the farms they come from (Chapter IV, Art. 22). Farm owners and vets must immediately report any increase

in mortality or suspicions of disease to the relevant authority (Art. 26). In cases of confirmed Marteiliosis (see below) the authorities will officially declare the farm as infected, establish a containment area with protection and surveillance zones and ban the restocking and movement of the mussels unless authorised by the competent authority.

Blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) are susceptible to infection with *Marteilia refringens*. Marteiliosis is listed as a notifiable aquatic animal disease by this Directive and by the OIE (World Organisation for Animal Health). *M. refringens* is a unicellular parasite affecting the digestive system of oysters and also blue mussels, *M. edulis*, as well as Mediterranean mussels (*M. galloprovincialis*). These parasite infections are directly related to high water temperature and low salinity. Enclosed farming areas are especially susceptible. The parasite can survive outside the host for several days up to 2–3 weeks, depending on the environmental conditions (Art. 80).

Testing of mussels for human consumption

For **microbiology**, the following regulations and limits apply (Class A - fresh consumption, Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs):

Species/Group	Limit
<i>E.coli</i>	5 of 5 samples < 230 MPN/100g meat Or max 1 sample > 230 MPN but <700 MPN/100g meat
Salmonellae	not detectable in a 25 g sample

Limits for **algae toxins** are (Regulation (EU) No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on hygiene rules for food of animal origin):

Poisoning	Toxins	Toxin producing species	Limit	Unit
Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP)	Domoic acid	<i>Pseudo-Nitzschia</i>	20	mg/kg
Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP)	Ocadaic acid and -derivatives, Dinophysistoxins	<i>Dinophysis</i> , <i>Prorocentrum</i>	0,16	mg/kg

	Azaspiroic acid		0,16	mg/kg
	Yessotoxins*		1,0	mg/kg
Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP)	Saxitoxins	<i>Alexandrium, Anabaena, Lyngbya, Oscillatoria</i>	0,80	mg/kg
Neurologic Shellfish Poisoning (NSP)*	Brevetoxins	<i>Karenia, Chatonella</i>	n.a.	n.a.

*For the time being NSPs and Yessotoxins are not within the list of required analysis. As it is presently under discussion it cannot be ruled out that it will be a requirement in the future.

Environmental toxins have to stay below the following limits (Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs):

Environmental toxin	Limit	Unit
Non-dioxin like PCBs (ndl PCBs)		
PCB 28		mg/kg wet weight
PCB 52		mg/kg wet weight
PCB 101		mg/kg wet weight
PCB 138		mg/kg wet weight
PCB 153		mg/kg wet weight
PCB 180		mg/kg wet weight
Sum of 6 ndl PCBs	0,075	mg/kg wet weight
Metals		
Lead (Pb)	1,5	mg/kg wet weight
Cadmium (Cd)	1	mg/kg wet weight
Mercury (Hg)	0,5	mg/kg wet weight
Dioxins and dl-PCB		
WHO-PCDD/F-TEQ (WHO-TEF 1997) upper bound	4	pg/g wet weight

WHO-PCDD/F-PCB-TEQ (WHO-TEF 1997) upper bound	8	pg/g wet weight
WHO-PCDD/F-TEQ (WHO-TEF 2005) upper bound	3,5	pg/g wet weight
WHO-PCDD/F-PCB-TEQ (WHO-TEF 2005) upper bound	6,5	pg/g wet weight
PAH		
Benzo(a)anthracen		µg/kg wet weight
Benzo(a)pyren	5	µg/kg wet weight
Benzo(b)fluoranthen		µg/kg wet weight
Chrysen		µg/kg wet weight
Sum of 4 PAHs	30	µg/kg wet weight

Mussels from class A production areas can be directly sold for human consumption, while live mussels as from areas B and C have to be cooked or relayed until reaching a satisfying microbial status and comply with all the requirements. Live bivalve molluscs from those areas which have not been cleaned or relayed may be sent to a processing plant where they must undergo a treatment designed to eliminate pathogenic micro-organisms. According to Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 the following treatment methods are permitted:

1. Sterilisation in hermetically sealed containers.
2. Heat treatments involving:
 - 2.a. Immersion in boiling water until the core temperature of the mussel meat reaches at least 90°C and maintenance of this minimum temperature for at least 90 seconds,
 - 2.b. Boiling for three to five minutes in a closed container at a temperature between 120°C and 160°C and a pressure between 2 and 5 kg/cm², followed by removal of the shell and freezing of the meat to a core temperature of -20°C and
 - 2.c. Boiling under pressure steam in a closed container, respecting the time and core temperature requirements set out in point (i).

A validated procedure must be used. Procedures based on HACCP principles must be in place to control the uniform distribution of heat.

Anyone who wants to market mussels for human consumption must register with the relevant authority as a food business operator. For preparation for shipping or further processing, the company may also need to be approved under food law - this depends on the type and extent of processing and/or distribution. According to Regulation (EU) 853/2004, Annex III Section VII Chapter I, a shipping centre is required for the mussels to be marketed, in which they must be provided with an identification label. The district in whose area the harvested mussels are prepared for sale is responsible for registering them as a food business operator. According to Regulation (EU) 852/2004, the main responsibility for the safety of food lies with the food business operator. This operator must meet all the requirements of food law. With regard to mussels, in addition to the general requirements of food law pursuant to Regulation (EU) 852/2004, the specific requirements for mussels pursuant to Regulation (EU) 853/2004 must be observed, for example, freshness, viability and contamination with marine biotoxins.

Mussels as animal feed

According to Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009, mussels can be used as pet food or animal feed, provided that the provenience, processing and end-use are safe and according to general rules for safety and animal welfare. Mussel meal is categorised as no 10.8.1 in the (EU) 68/2013 catalogue on feed and mussel meal producers must keep a record of the products and transport.

If mussels (or fish, crustaceans and other molluscs) are to be used as animal feed, they must first be handled after harvesting as animal by-products of category 3 in accordance with Article 10 of Regulation (EC) 1069/2009. This means that this part of the harvest must be stored separately from products that are to be sold as food in order to avoid contamination. The transportation of the animal by-products to the processing plant must come from a person in accordance with Article 23 Entrepreneurs registered under Regulation (EC) 1069/2009. From the time of processing in a feed plant, feed law applies.

Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 laying down health rules for risk prevention and minimisation to human and animal health and for a safe food and feed chain. It applies to animal by-products and derived products along the entire process chain that are not intended for human consumption, however not to empty shells of shellfish (without soft tissue and flesh).

Mussel and mussel meal producers must keep a record of the products they despatch, transport or receive, along with the required documentation (Art. 21) (commercial documents and health certificates). Mussel and mussel meal producers must inform national authorities of the products and premises they use during the manufacturing

chain. Depending on the level of health risk they pose to the public or animals, animal by-products are classified in three categories, while mussel meal belongs to the category “small risk”.

Annex IV of the Regulation EU/142/2011 describes detailed requirements for processing enterprises (waste water treatment; special requirements like the presence of an installation to check the presence of packaging material or metallic pieces; hygiene and processing requirements; standard and alternative processing methods).

The Organic Production Regulation

The Organic Production Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 2018/848) lays down a legal framework for organic products, containing basic objectives and general principles for organic farming. It also illustrates the rules on production, labelling, controls and trade with non-EU countries.

Labels such as Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) certified and Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) certified encompass the EU standard, adding particular and specific values such as animal welfare or social standards.

Due to its immanent environmental benefits, organic production is a relatively easy task for mussel farms. Organic production rules out the use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in all forms, and any treatment by ionizing radiation. It is required that the mussels have been recruited and reared in organic holdings, that husbandry practices meet the developmental, physiological and behavioral needs of mussels and that negative environmental impacts are minimized. Moreover, mussels must receive all their nutritional requirements from nature. If the yearly production exceeds 20 tonnes, an appropriate assessment has to be carried out. Organic and non-organic production units must be kept apart by a distance set by the member state. This distance should consider the natural surroundings, water flow, distances, and tidal currents. Aquaculture animals cannot be classified as organic if they are raised in sites or areas that the member state authorities have deemed unsuitable for such practices.

National legislation

Swedish legislation

Shipping rules

The Maritime Shipping law controls the use of ships on national and international waterways on the basis of the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea. Vessels must be equipped according to SJÖFS 1999:8 with appropriate life-saving appliances, pollution prevention, fire protection, navigation and communication equipment as well as navigation lights and sound signal appliances.

Danish legislation

Site selection

Danish territorial waters are fully planned, and areas designated for mussel production can be derived from the [official map](#).

Permission for mussel farming is granted by the Danish Fisheries Agency, an authority

Figure 2: The uses of the Danish territorial waters. Source: <https://havplan.dk/da/page/info>.

under the Ministry of Food, Agriculture, and Fisheries. With the executive order for mussel farming from 2021, a moratorium was introduced. This moratorium is still in effect and is not expected to be lifted before potentially in the summer 2025. The moratorium was partly prompted by dissatisfaction among municipalities regarding their lack of influence over where mussel farming permits were granted. In particular, farming with the Smart Farm system caused dissatisfaction in the municipalities, especially due to the system's high visibility in the landscape.

Acquiring a license for mussel production on longlines or SmartFarm systems applied before the moratorium decided in 2021, requires that the chosen area for production is reviewed for possible disturbances on protected species, in accordance with Natura 2000 law. An assessment of whether the establishment and operation of a mussel farm could harm a Natura 2000 area is part of the process for obtaining a permit. The

Natura 2000 regulations are thus integrated into Danish fisheries and aquaculture legislation.

Applications are evaluated in relation to the Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC.) to determine whether a mussel farm could hinder achieving Good Environmental Status (GES), which is the target for all Danish water bodies. Particular attention is given to the impact on eelgrass, which is a key indicator species. Consequently, a management practice has been established in Denmark, where a depth limit has been set for each water body, specifying the depth to which eelgrass must be able to extend. As a result, it is currently not possible to obtain a new permit for mussel farming if it is located at a depth shallower than the target depth limit for eelgrass. This despite the fact that the current distribution of eelgrass is at significantly shallower depths than the target depth limit, and several independent studies indicate that mussel filtration can promote a greater depth distribution of eelgrass.

To obtain a permit for mussel farming, the area where the permit is sought must be designated as a production area. Danish waters used for shellfish production are divided into areas, each subjected to an overall screening for microbiological and chemical contamination, which is repeated annually. Thus, the designation and testing of new production areas are required if a permit is sought outside already designated production areas. It should also be noted that it is the responsibility of the mussel producer to ensure that the mussels produced are safe, even if production takes place in an approved area.

By law mussel farming cannot be used as a nutrient-catch culture for marine fish farms (IMTA). Furthermore, it is complicated to combine mussel farming with farming of seaweed, as the permits for seaweed are issued by another ministry, and may conflict with the zoning of the coastal area.

In legislation no. 1693 of 15/12/2016 25 specific production areas for mussel farming on longlines and SmartFarm systems are defined. Most fjords in Denmark are open for mussel production, as long as the requirements for microbiological and algae testing are met. Thus, licenses for mussel production in these areas are normally given, if the environmental pre-analysis concludes no disturbances to protected plants and animal species. In Denmark, the production of mussels on longlines or SmartFarm systems are recognised as more sustainable methods of production than harvesting from wild populations because mussels grown in the water column will give a minimal risk to bottom ecosystems.

Permission for mussel farming on both longlines and SmartFarm systems and from wild populations may be restricted, if fishing takes place in or near Natura2000 areas, where significant, negative effects on certain species or habitats are unavoidable. The

production of mussels as Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture in eutrophic waters is approved for compensation use in mariculture.

Environmental permit

To achieve the goals of the WFD the Danish waters have been divided into water areas, each managed under the respective municipal authority. Each municipality presents goals specific to these water areas, which were already supposed to be achieved by the year 2021. In each water area a basic analysis of environmental factors, i.e. endangered species, nutrient flow etc., has been conducted with the purpose of creating a fundamental understanding of the environmental status of the different areas. These form the foundation of the Danish Water Area Plans, which have the sole purpose of describing environmental factors in the area, so that environmental improvement, in accordance with the WFD, is more achievable.

Mussels for human consumption

Production of mussels in coastal zones and fjords in Denmark is subject to legislation no. 1321 28/11/2024, wherein it is described that the water body, in which mussels are either harvested from bottom cultures or from suspended production facilities such as longlines etc., must be tested for toxic algae. Furthermore, the microbiological conditions must also be monitored, to ensure less health risks when the mussels are fished or harvested and sold.

Certification

The national Danish regulation 2168 of 23/11/2021 on organic production and labelling of organic products implements the Council Regulation (EC) No 2018/848 organic production and labelling of organic products.

German legislation

Maritime planning

German maritime water legislation is divided into i) maritime shipping legislation and ii) waterways legislation (Federal waterways act (Bundeswasserstraßengesetz (WaStrG) 194), both of which are relevant for mussel aquaculture purposes. According to §1 WaStrG, inland and maritime waterways are federal waterways. Maritime waterways are the German territorial coastal waters (12 nm zone). Within the 12 nautical mile limit, i.e. in the area of the territorial sea, responsibility for the approval of mussel farms rests with the German Federal coastal states. Mussel aquaculture located in these waters must respect the German maritime waterways legislation, for example covering the installation and operation of navigation signs, water level reports, or ice control.

Territorial waters: The waterways and shipping agency (Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes, WSV), is a department of the Ministry for Traffic (Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verkehr) and is responsible for the

administration of federal waterways and safety of ship traffic. For the Baltic Sea, the subordinated "Wasser- und Schifffahrtsamt (WSA) Ostsee in Lübeck is responsible.

River and shipping police permit

According to the **German Offshore Installations Law** (Seeanlagengesetz (SeeAnlG 202) mussel farms in the EEZ are maritime installations (§ 1 (2) No. 3 SeeAnlG) and therefore must have the approval of the SeeAnlG. The approval procedure must respect the principles and current aims (or aims in process) of spatial planning (§ 6 (2) SeeAnlG). The required written application for approval must contain a detailed description of the installation and its operation including the description of safety and precautionary measures. It must contain drawings, explanations and plans of the mussel farm. The BSH may also request an expert opinion about technical the state-of-the-art and safety requirements (§ 6 (3) SeeAnlG). The approval may be time-limited and include incidental provisions (§ 6 (4) SeeAnlG).

Environmental permit

According to Section 40 (1) of the State Fisheries Act for Schleswig-Holstein (LFischG) of February 10, 1996, last amended on October 26, 2011 (GVObI. Schl.-H. 2011, p. 295), a **permit from the state of Schleswig-Holstein** is required to practice mussel farming, issued by the MLLV. When establishing aquaculture facilities, the existing diverse competition for use (e.g. tourism, transport, fishing, military and military legacy) and the existing nutrient pollution of the Baltic Sea and the resulting need to improve the environmental condition must be considered.

According to the strategy for developing sustainable aquaculture in Schleswig-Holstein (Strategie zur Entwicklung einer nachhaltigen Aquakultur in Schleswig Holstein, 2014), locations in nature reserves are ruled out and the search for locations should primarily take place outside of Natura 2000 areas (see **Natura 2000**). A fee is charged for granting permission to farm mussels (between 25 € and 500 €).

Natura 2000

The Natura 2000 network encompasses to a large extent other nature-protected areas at federal and/or state levels. For a more detailed view refer to the list of naturae protected areas in Schleswig-Holstein and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern.

Figure 3: Natura 2000 (bird directive and habitat directive) areas in the German part of the North Sea and Baltic Sea. Source: Bundesanstalt für Naturschutz (BfN (<https://www.bfn.de/daten-und-fakten/marine-natura-2000-gebiete-der-deutschen-nord-und-ostsee>))

Fisheries permit

The Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) is responsible for fisheries control and surveillance (§ 2 (1) SeeFischG). The Federal Fisheries Act does not specify aquaculture explicitly but empowers the Federal States to adopt their own fishery rules. Official announcements for the fisheries sector issued by BLE have to be respected.

The State Fisheries Act in Schleswig-Holstein is also applicable within the Federal States coastal waters (12 nm) (§1 LFischG) for mussel cultivation. The Coastal Fisheries Directive (KüFVO) specifies the fisheries in the coastal area of Schleswig-Holstein. According to § 2, 3, 5 and 15, mussel culture areas may be established for mussel seeding, rearing, harvesting and storage. The KüFVO also determines rules for the labelling of mussel culturing areas and equipment. Marker buoys require radar reflectors, as well as the inscription of the mussel farmer name. Details are controlled by the superior fisheries authority (Oberste Fischreibehörde).

Similarly, the Fishing law for Mecklenburg-Vorpommern (Landesfischereigesetz - LFischG M-V) and the directive for coastal fisheries in the coastal areas of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern (Küstenfischereiverordnung - KüFVO M-V) regulate the practice of coastal fisheries. There is no particular mention of mussel farming.

Production areas

The basic requirements for the designation of new production areas and their continuous monitoring are regulated in Annex II, Chapter II of Regulation (EU) 854/2004. The regulations for placing mussels on the market can be found in Regulation (EU) 853/2004, Annex III, Section VII.

Before a mussel production area can be newly designated, the responsible authority must classify the area using a so-called sanitary survey. The sanitary survey takes into account sources of pollution of all origins as well as their distribution patterns through currents, tides and water structures. The competent authority draws up a list of sources of pollution of human or animal origin that could also be responsible for the contamination of the production area and checks the quantities of organic pollutants released in the different periods of the year, according to the seasonal variations of the human and animal populations in the catchment area, the recorded rainfall, wastewater treatment, etc. In addition, the characteristics of the pollutant cycle must be determined, taking into account current patterns, deep-sea measurements and the tidal cycle in the production area.

The sanitary survey also includes the determination of suitable representative sampling points, since the mussel harvest is subject to strict monitoring even after the initial release of a production area.

This classification (A, B, or C) has consequences for the direct marketing of the mussels; a possible stay of the mussels in a cleaning centre could be necessary (Regulation (EU) 853/2004, Annex III Section VII Chapter II). Since mussels are extremely sensitive foods, all production areas must be sampled regularly. Currently, in SH, samples must be examined microbiologically and for marine biotoxins every week before and during the entire harvest. The tests are mandatory and represent a significant cost factor. Monitoring also extends to organic and chemical pollutants as well as regular water tests for the presence of toxin-producing phytoplankton.

Vessels

The Maritime Shipping law controls the use of ships on national and international waterways on the basis of the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (Kollisionsverhütungsregeln - KVR 205) in conjunction with the respective implementation regulation (SeeStrVO) 206 and the German Traffic Regulations for Navigable Maritime Waterways (Seeschiffverkehrsstraßenordnung (SeeSchStrO) 207) including the WSD notifications as well as concerning particular traffic rules in national parks and nature conservation areas.

For mussel farms, it is of relevance concerning the boat traffic to and from the farm to the shore, as well as the requirements for the vessels concerning safety and design. The German fishing vessels (and aquaculture vessels) of less than 24 m in length are covered by German law. The German Ship Safety Act (Schiffssicherheitsgesetz

(SchSG) 208) and the Ship Safety Regulation (Schiffssicherheitsverordnung (SchSV) 209) include ship safety requirements regarding the design and the construction of the vessel depending on the ship’s size, hull form, fishing gear and intended area of operation.

FUNDING AND SUPPORT

Due to its positive impact on water quality and the local economy, mussel farming might receive support from regional, national or even international programmes. These often focus on innovations (R&D, R&I) programmes, and are subject to the respective political focus. The table below lists funding opportunities and contacts for further inquiries.

Examples of places of contact and further information for assistance and funding:

Area	Relevant programs	Links
EU level	The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) helps achieve sustainable fisheries and conserve marine biological resources, leading to food security through the supply of seafood products, growth of a sustainable blue economy, and healthy, safe and sustainably managed seas and oceans.	www.fi-compass.eu/funds/emfaf https://lfst.dk/tilskud/soeg-tilskud/tilskudsguide www.interreg.de/INTERREG2021/DE/Startseite/home_node.html
DE Schleswig-Holstein	The EMFAF program in Schleswig-Holstein is the Landesamt für Landwirtschaft und nachhaltige Landentwicklung, LLnL.	www.schleswig-holstein.de/DE/landesregierung/ministerien-behoerden/LLNL/LLNL_node.html
DE Mecklenburg - Vorpommern	The MKLLU is the place of contact for EMFAF program of EU in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	www.regierung-mv.de/Landesregierung/lm/
Multi-national (EU)	Interreg programs, focusing on the cooperation between neighbouring EU countries (such as Denmark-	https://interreg.eu/ www.interreg.de/INTERREG2021/DE/Startseite/home_node.html

	Germany, Poland-Germany, the Baltic Sea region, etc.)	<i>ml</i>
International	Certification initiatives such as MSC, ASC and similar regularly offer funding opportunities, such as MSCs Ocean Stewardship Fund or ASCs Improver Programme.	https://www.msc.org/what-we-are-doing/our-collective-impact/ocean-stewardship-fund https://asc-aqua.org/producers/farmers-support-improver-programme/
International	Hatch BLUE is an investment agency providing direct investments and support programmes.	https://www.hatch.blue/investments#current-funds
International	Ocean Collective is an investment agency providing direct investments and support programmes.	https://www.oceancollective.se/
DK	The Danish Innovation Fund	https://innovationsfonden.dk/en
NO, DK, SE	Nordic Council of Ministers	https://www.norden.org/en/funding-opportunities
DK	The Danish Green Investment Fund is an independent state loan fund with the purpose of co-financing economically viable projects that facilitate and support the sustainable development of our society.	https://gronfond.dk/en/
DE	Die Fachagentur Nachwachsende Rohstoffe als Projektträger des BMEL (FNR); The purpose of the FNR is to make an effective and continuous contribution to the development and use of renewable raw materials, particularly with regard to competing uses, direct and indirect land use effects, biomass conversions and partial and overarching sustainability concepts.	www.fnr.de

DE	Deutsche Bundesumweltstiftung (DBU) supports projects, start-ups and PhD students that focus on innovative, exemplary and solution-oriented projects to protect the environment with special consideration for small and medium-sized businesses.	<i>Osnabrück, An der Bornau 2, 49090 Osnabrück,</i> <i>www.dbu.de</i>
DE, Schleswig-Holstein	Wirtschafts- und Technologieförderung Schleswig-Holstein (WTSH).	<i>www.foerderdatenbank.de/FDB/Content/DE/Foerderprogramm/Land/Schleswig-Holstein/foerderung-der-aquakultur.html</i>
DE	Local or communal administration e.g. environmental departments or others. A very useful number within Germany is the “Behördennummer” (Administration number).	<i>Tel. 115</i>
DE, Mecklenburg - Vorpommern	Ministerium für Klimaschutz, Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume und Umwelt (MKLLU) provides support in fishing matters. This is based on the guidelines for granting subsidies for fisheries, aquaculture and the fishing industry in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern as part of the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (FischFöRL EMFAF M-V).	<i>www.regierung-mv.de/Landesregierung/lm/</i>
SE	Hållbara vattenbruk: The program aims to promote environmentally, economically and socially sustainable fisheries and aquaculture in Sweden. The program includes support for projects and investments that contribute to meeting the goals.	<i>https://jordbruksverket.se/stod/eus-politik-for-jordbruk-och-fiske/havs--fiskeri--och-vattenbruksprogrammet</i>

SE	The purpose of the Postcode Lottery Foundation is to promote sustainable development by supporting non-profit organizations both in Sweden and internationally, which promote positive social development or seek long-term solutions to global challenges.	https://postkodstiftelsen.se/so k-stod/
SE	Formas is a Swedish government research council for sustainable development. They fund research and innovation, develop strategies, perform analyses and conduct evaluations.	https://formas.se/en/start-page/apply-for-funding/all-calls.html
SE	Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management (SwAM – HaV) posts calls relevant for sustainable water projects.	https://www.havochvatten.se/bidrag-utlysningar-och-anslag.html
SE	Local measures for a better marine and water environment can receive support through LOVA grants. The grant can be applied for from the county administrative board and goes to municipalities, associations and other non-profit organizations.	https://www.havochvatten.se/bidrag-utlysningar-och-anslag/havs--och-vattenmiljoanslaget-anslag-111/lova--lokala-vattenvarsprojekt.html
SE	Nature protection agency – “The Climate Move”.	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/bidrag/klimatklivet/

ANNEX 1: OVERVIEW OF SWEDISH PROCEDURE

ANNEX 2: OVERVIEW OF DANISH PROCEDURE

ANNEX 3: OVERVIEW OF GERMAN PROCEDURE

